

Structure of Two New Saponins from Stem-Bark of *Anthocephalus cadamba* Miq.

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Two new saponins (C and D) have been isolated from stem-bark of *Anthocephalus cadamba* Miq. From the results of permethylation and periodate-oxidation studies, as well as by application of Klyne's rule the structures of saponin C and saponin D are established as β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3)- α -L-fucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3) quinovic acid and α -L-rhamnopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4) β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 2) [β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)] α -L-fucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3) quinovic acid respectively.

ANTHOCEPHALUS *cadamba* Miq. (Rubiaceae) is a large deciduous tree found all over India.

The stem-bark of the plant is reported¹ to be used as tonic, febrifuge astringent and also used in snake-bite. Isolation of saponin-A and saponin B from the stem-bark of the plant has already been reported^{2,3}. This paper deals with the structure elucidation of saponin C and saponin D (minor constituents).

Saponin C: A new saponin $C_{48}H_{76}O_{19}$, m. p. 295° (d) $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 4.24^\circ$ (EtOH) which on acid hydrolysis yielded D-glucose and L-fucose in 2 : 1 molar ratio and the aglycone part was identified as quinovic acid (m.p., m.m.p., IR, NMR, MS). Complete hydrolysis of saponin-C dimethyl ester with 7% H_2SO_4 yielded quinovic acid dimethyl ester, D-glucose and L-fucose. This showed that the sugars were linked to 3-hydroxy of quinovic acid. Quantitative estimation of the genin (gravimetric) and sugars by Dubois method⁴ showed the aglycone, D-glucose and L-fucose in the molar ratio of 1.1 : 2.2 : 0.98. Partial hydrolysis of saponin C dimethyl ester with 1% H_2SO_4 followed by re-esterification yielded beside other products dimethyl ester of quinovic acid- α -L-fucopyranoside $C_{38}H_{60}O_9$, m.p. 240° (d), $[\alpha]_D^{27} + 6.4^\circ$ (EtOH). This glycoside on acid hydrolysis yielded dimethyl ester of quinovic acid and L-fucose in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The structure of this glycoside was established as dimethyl ester of quinovic acid- α -L-fucopyranoside by permethylation and periodate-oxidation studies. The MS of its triacetate showed fairly stable molecular ions, showing characteristic fragmentation of Δ^{12} -ursene and Δ^{12} -oleanene type and also 6-deoxyhexopyranoside acetate type⁵. These results showed that L-fucopyranose unit is directly linked to the aglycone. Complete methylation of dimethyl ester of the saponin was achieved by prolonged treatment with Hakomori's procedure⁶. After acid hydrolysis of the permethylate the sugar part was separated into

three pure fractions by preparative paper chromatography and as identified as 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose, 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-glucose and 2, 4-di-O-methyl-L-fucose. Molar ratio of the methylated sugars was determined to be 1.0 : 1.02 : 0.98 by alkaline hypiodite method⁷.

Periodate-oxidation of saponin C dimethyl ester was carried out at room temperature. Consumption of oxidant and liberation of formic acid were found to be 3.08 and 1.01 mol. respectively.

Hence the structure of saponin C dimethyl ester can be represented as D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)-D-glucopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 3)-L-fucopyranosyl(1 \rightarrow 3) quinovic acid dimethyl ester.

Further support to the sequence of the sugars in the parent glycoside was obtained by subjecting the periodate-oxidised saponin C dimethyl ester to acid hydrolysis and the hydrolysate was examined for sugars. Identification of only L-fucose supported the structure as deduced above.

The configuration of the anomeric carbon atoms of the sugars in saponin C dimethyl ester were deduced by application of Klyne's rule of molecular rotation⁸ (Table 1) and was found to be α for L-fucose and β -for D-glucose. Hence the structure of saponin C was assigned as β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3)- α -L-fucopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 3)-quinovic acid(I).

Saponin D: Saponin D dimethyl ester (IIa) $C_{56}H_{90}O_{28}$, m.p. 302° (d) $[\alpha]_D^{28} - 21^\circ$ on complete hydrolysis yielded quinovic acid dimethyl ester, D-glucose, L-rhamnose and L-fucose. This established the direct linkage of sugar with 3-hydroxyl of quinovic acid. Quantitative analysis of the genin

TABLE—1 MOLECULAR ROTATION CALCULATIONS OF SAPONIN-C-DIMETHYL ESTER (Ia)

Compound	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$
Methyl- β -D-glucopyranoside	-34.2°	-66°
" " "	Literature value°	
" " "	-34.2°	-66°
" " "	Observed value	
" " "	+6.4°	+42.2°
For dimethyl ester of α -L-fucopyranoside of quinovic acid (III)		
For compd. (Ia)	Calculated value	-89.8°
For compd. (Ia)	Observed value	-90.5°
For compd. (Ia)	-9.2°	

(gravimetric) and sugars (colorimetric) showed the aglycone, D-glucose, L-rhamnose and L-fucose in the molar ratio of 1.1 : 2.2 : 1.2 : 1.09. Dimethyl ester of quinovic acid- α -L-fucopyranoside as in saponin-C was isolated from partial hydrolysis (by 1% H₂SO₄) product of saponin D. Isolation of this glycoside established the direct link of L-fucose with the aglycone. Permethylation and hydrolysis of the product yielded four pure sugar fractions which were easily identified as 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose, 2, 3, 6-tri-O-methyl-D-glucose, 2, 3, 4-tri-O-methyl-L-rhamnose and 3-O-methyl-L-fucose in the molar of 0.98 : 1.2 : 1.1 : 1.01.

On periodate oxidation the dimethyl ester of saponin-D consumed 5.11 mol of periodate with liberation of 2.08 mol. of formic acid.

Therefore, the structure of saponin-D can be represented as α -L-rhamnopyranosyl (1→4)- β -D-glucopyranosyl(1→2) [β -D-glucopyranosyl (1→4)] α -L-fucopyranosyl (1→3) quinovic acid.

Isolation of only L-fucose from the hydrolysate of periodate-oxidised saponin-D dimethyl ester also gave additional support to the proposed structure of saponin-D.

With regard to the configuration of saponin glycosidic linkages it is a general observation that D-sugars occur with β -glycosidic linkages and L-sugars with α -glycosidic linkages¹⁰.

The calculation of the molecular rotation (Table 2) of the dimethyl ester of saponin-D on the basis of Klyne's rule also support the type of linkages assigned. Hence the structure of saponin, D can be represent as (II).

- I, R=R¹=COOH, R'¹=H ..
 II, R=R¹=COOH, R'¹=D-glucopyranose, 3= α -L-rhamnopyranose, linkage bet. 2 to 1 is (1→2)
 Ia, R=R¹=COOCH₃, R'¹=H
 IIa, R=R¹=COOCH₃, R'¹=D-glucopyranose, 3= α -L-rhamnopyranose, linkage bet. 2 to 1 is (1→2)

TABLE—2 MOLECULAR ROTATION CALCULATIONS OF SAPONIN-D DIMETHYL-ESTER(IIa)

Compound	$[\alpha]_D$	$[M]_D$
Methyl- β -D-glucopyranoside	-34.2°	
" " "	Literature value°	
" " "	-34.2°	-66°
" " "	Observed value	-66°
Methyl- α -L-rhamnopyranoside	-62.3°	-111°
" " "	Observed value	
For dimethyl ester of α -L-fucopyranoside quinovic acid (III)		
For compd. (IIa)	+6.4°	+42.2°
For compd. (IIa)	Calculated value	-200.8°
For compd. (IIa)	Observed value	
For compd. (IIa)	-21°	-237.3°

Experimental

All specific rotations are equilibrium values. All evaporations were carried out in vacuum at 35-40°. Whatman no. 1 paper was used for analytical paper chromatography and Whatman No. 3 MM paper for preparative chromatography.

The solvent mixture (v/v) used for partition chromatography of sugars were: A, n-butanol : acetic acid : water (4 : 1 : 5), upper layer; B, n-butanol : pyridine : water (6 : 4 : 3); C, ethyl acetate : pyridine : water (8 : 2 : 1); D, n-butanol : ethanol : water (5 : 1 : 4), upper layer. Spray reagents were (a) aqueous saturated aniline oxalate and (b) alkaline silver nitrate solution.

Isolation of pure saponin C and D :

Air dried powdered stem-bark of *A. cadamba* was defatted with pet. ether and then successively extracted with chloroform and methanol in a Soxhlet extractor. The methanolic extract on removal of the solvent yielded a brown semi-solid material. This material was shaken with aqueous potassium hydroxide solution (5%) for one hour and then

filtered, residue obtained was negligible. The filtrate was acidified with hydrochloric acid when a brown precipitate was obtained. The solid was filtered, washed until acid free and dried to a brown powder. This powder was dissolved in ethanol, mixed with paper pulp dried and extracted successively with ether, ethylacetate and ethanol. Major part was collected in ethyl acetate fraction. The material was dissolved in minimum vol. of methanol and poured into a large vol. of ether. The brown solid was collected and the process was repeated until a white powder was obtained. This material was chromatographed on silica gel and saponin C and D were eluted with chloroform : methanol 95 : 5 and 92 : 8 respectively. The pure saponin C (I) and D (II) were crystallised from chloroform-methanol-ether mixture having m. p. 295° (d) $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 4.24^\circ$ (EtOH) and m. p. 312° (d) $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 8.4^\circ$ (EtOH) respectively.

Dimethyl esters of saponins : Each saponins (500 mg) in 800 ml of methanol was treated with excess of an ethereal solution of diazomethane. The products were purified by column chromatography on silica gel. Dimethyl ester of saponin C (Ia) was crystallised from chloroform : methanol, m.p. 290-91° (d) $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 9.2^\circ$ (EtOH). Found : C, 60.42 ; H, 8.21%, $C_{50}H_{80}O_{16}$ requires C, 60.97 ; H, 8.13) : Dimethyl ester of saponin D (IIa) was crystallised in micro needles from methanol-chloroform, m. p. 302° (d), $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 21^\circ$ (EtOH). (Found : C, 60.1 ; H, 7.8, $C_{50}H_{80}O_{16}$ requires C, 59.4 ; H, 7.9%).

Identification of aglycone and sugars : Hydrolysis of Ia and IIa with H_2SO_4 (7%), yielded the genin as needles from methanol, m.p. 175-76°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 121.1^\circ$ (EtOH), and identified as dimethyl ester of quinovic acid (m. p., m. m.p., IR, NMR, MS). The sugars in aqueous portion were identified as D-glucose and L-fucose in case of Ia and D-glucose, L-rhamnose and L-fucose in case of IIa (solvent systems, A, B and C).

Partial hydrolysis of Ia and IIa : 400 mg of each was refluxed with 50 ml of 1% H_2SO_4 in methanol for one hr and the product isolated was treated with excess of ethereal diazomethane and chromatographed over silica gel. Benzene eluted dimethyl ester of quinovic acid and chloroform : methanol (99 : 1) eluted dimethyl ester of quinovic acid- α -L-fucopyranoside(III), crystallised from methanol-ether, m.p. 240° (d) $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 6.4^\circ$ (EtOH) (Found : C, 70.1 ; H, 9.4 ; $C_{58}H_{80}O_9$ requires C, 69.1 ; H, 9.1%). Permethylation of III and hydrolysis yielded 2, 3, 4-tri-O-methyl- α -L-fucopyranoside syrup, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 127^\circ$ (H_2O) (Lit.¹¹, m.p. 36°, $[\alpha]_D - 128^\circ$ (H_2O)).

On periodate oxidation it consumed 2.1 mols. of periodate with liberation of 1.09 mol of formic acid. Mass spectra of triacetate yielded mol. ion at m/e 785 M+ and also peaks at m/e 273 and 111 which are characteristic of acetates of 6-deoxyhexopyranoside⁵.

Permethylation (Hakomori's method⁶) and hydrolysis of Ia and IIa : 50% sodium hydride dispersion in oil (ca. 120 mg) was suspended in dimethyl sulphoxide (12 ml) and kept in an oil bath at 80° for one hour. A solution of saponin-dimethyl ester (70 mg) in dimethyl sulphoxide (2.5 ml) was then added gradually and the mixture was kept at 80° for one hour with constant stirring. It was cooled in ice and methyl iodide (1.5 ml) was added in drops. The fully methylated product isolated in the usual way (syrup) showed no absorption band in the region of 3500-3600 cm^{-1} in IR. The fully methylated product was hydrolysed with $N-H_2SO_4$ for 10 hrs on a boiling water bath. The hydrolysate was neutralised with $BaCO_3$, filtered, deionised and evaporated to a syrup. The syrup was separated into three and four pure fractions in case of Ia and IIa respectively by preparative paper chromatography. In case of Ia, the methylated sugars were identified as 2, 3, 4, 6-tetra-O-methyl-D glucose, m.p. 92-93° $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 81^\circ$ (H_2O). (Lit.¹², m.p. 96° $[\alpha]_D + 84^\circ$), 2, 3, 6-tri-O-methyl-D-glucose m. p. 120-21°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 68.9^\circ$ (H_2O) (Lit.¹³, m.p. 121-23°, $[\alpha]_D + 70^\circ$) and 2,4-di-O-methyl-L-fucose, m.p. 129-30°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 84^\circ$ (H_2O , (Lit.¹⁴, m.p. 131-32° $[\alpha]_D - 85^\circ$)). Molar ratio of the methylated sugars was found to be 1.0 : 1.02 : 0.98 by alkaline hypoiodite method⁷.

In case of IIa, the methylated sugars were identified as 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-glucose and 2, 3, 6-tri-O-methyl-glucose (m.p. and $[\alpha]_D$ values are as in the above), 2,3,4-tri-O-methyl-L-rhamnose, syrup, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 24.1^\circ$ (H_2O) (Lit. 15a, 15b syrup $[\alpha]_D + 26^\circ$) and 3-O-methyl-L-fucose, syrup $[\alpha]_D^{25} - 92.8^\circ$ (H_2O) (Lit.¹⁶ syrup, $[\alpha]_D - 94^\circ$). Methylated sugars were also compared with authentic samples. Molar ratio of methylated sugars in case of IIa was determined to be 0.98 : 1.2 : 1.1 : 1.01.

Periodate-oxidation studies on dimethyl ester of saponins (C and D) were carried out with 0.1 M sodium metaperiodate solution. Consumption of the oxidant was determined spectrophotometrically¹⁷ and was found to become constant in 30 hrs and 40 hrs corresponding to 3.08 and 5.11 mols for Ia and IIa respectively. The liberation of formic acid were estimated in the usual way¹⁸ and become constant in the same time corresponding to 1.01 and 2.08 mol for Ia and IIa respectively.

Periodate-oxidised Ia and IIa were hydrolysed

with $\text{N-H}_2\text{SO}_4$ and sugars were identified from hydrolysates. Only L-fucose was detected in both the cases.

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